

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

UNLOCKING FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING: KEY PRINCIPLES FOR SUCCESS IN MULTILINGUALISM

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Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

Mastering a foreign language is a skill that requires significant effort and prolonged dedication. Success in this endeavor primarily depends on the effectiveness of the methods used. Language learning methods shape the model of the learning process, which is conducted using a variety of teaching techniques. Only by understanding the processes of language acquisition can we create effective language learning methods. Understanding the processes that occur in the human mind, especially those related to language acquisition and specifically foreign language acquisition, requires observation and analysis. Observing and analyzing the applied teaching techniques can help derive the principles for language acquisition and success in multilingualism. The principles for language learning are broadly applicable and stable, but they vary in their effectiveness for different individuals.

Keywords: Foreign Language Learning; Multilingualism; Language Acquisition Principles; Vocabulary Acquisition; Cognitive Processes in Language Learning; Language Teaching Principles; Practical Language Use; Self-Evaluation in Language Learning

1. Introduction

Studying and mastering a foreign language is a complex process that demands significant effort and rational actions from both teachers and students alike. Over time, students accumulate, develop, and maintain two key categories of knowledge in a foreign language: vocabulary and grammar. The deepest understanding of a language often comes through academic study, yet this alone is insufficient for its active and successful application.

Language is a skill that becomes an integral part of human consciousness, like movement, playing a musical instrument, or working with technology. It develops because of intellectual growth and the necessity for effective communication with the surrounding environment. Even though communication can take various forms, such as gestures, facial expressions, and written text, language remains the most powerful and universal tool for human interaction.

Mastering a foreign language requires not only theoretical knowledge but also skills acquired through practice and experience. Human ingenuity enables many individuals to master not just one, but multiple foreign languages. The ability to acquire a foreign language may resemble the process of acquiring one's native language, yet it also depends on the methodology and educational environment in which learning takes place.

Studying foreign languages presents a challenge that engages scholars from various fields of study.

Mitchell, R. & Myles, F. (2004, p.12). *Second language learning processes have always been influenced by arguments on basic themes in human learning in general, and this has been the case from the beginning*

of educational discourse. An example of this is the argument between nature and nurture. What percentage of human learning is a result of natural predispositions, sometimes known as some type of genetic pre-programming, and what percentage is a result of social and cultural events that have an impact on us as we grow up? [1]

The foundation of the learning process in studying a foreign language lies in principles that form the basis for successful language acquisition. Various teaching methods and techniques can apply these universal principles.

This article discusses key principles for successful foreign language acquisition and proposes strategies for their application in educational practice.

2. Methodology of Research

- The author's research on himself as an object with the subject of learning foreign language vocabulary.
- The results of a survey, conducted using questionnaires distributed in a special Facebook group, support the research on the topic. We distribute these surveys to the international community of polyglots, philologists, translators, foreign language teachers, and foreign language learners.
- Critical analysis of another author's research.

3. Principles for Learning a Foreign Language

- The first and most important principle is that the learners must be able to evaluate their progress in all aspects by choosing the right strategies for quick, easy, and effective acquisition of the foreign language they are studying. According to Jones, O. (2024). *It is*

also very important to apply student-led learning technical skills, which are a modern style of learning that emphasizes self-directed education, creativity, and discovery rather than rote memorization or traditional lecture-style education.[2]

Analysis: Proper self-assessment is key to successful learning. Learners should be able to recognize their progress and adapt their methods to achieve maximum efficiency.

- Second Principle: It is essential to understand how people acquire their native language. This knowledge is vital because the successful acquisition of a foreign language, regardless of the methods and techniques used, fundamentally does not differ from what nature has given us. All principles and methods for learning a foreign language that contradict or deviate from human nature are wrong. According to Krashen, S., (1982, p.12). *In recent years, one of the most exciting discoveries in language acquisition research has been made. It has been found that the acquisition of grammatical structures proceeds in a predictable manner. order. Acquirers of a given language tend to acquire certain grammatical structures early, and others later.*[3]

Analysis: Learning a foreign language should reflect the natural process of learning one's native language. This implies that methods that deviate from this process may be less effective.

- Third Principle: Children acquire their native language through their parents' care and communication. Instead of memorizing and repeating what they hear, children learn the language by understanding what their parents say and demonstrating in a suggestive and demonstrative manner. Parents are their first teachers in everything, including language. According to Rimbey, Ch. & McKay, A (2023). *Language acquisition is the process by which we learn to communicate effectively and meaningfully in a target language. How this happens and the process is facilitated are both highly contested research topics. There are four main theories of language acquisition: Linguistic theory; Behaviorist theory; Cognitive theory; and Interactionist theory. All theories have strengths and weaknesses.* [4]

Analysis: Practical use and understanding of the language in everyday contexts are key for natural acquisition. Parents play a crucial role as the first teachers, helping children learn the language through contextual examples.

- Fourth Principle: Regardless of the method of learning a foreign language and the methodology of teaching it, the mental processes in the human mind occur in the same way, predetermined by nature. According to Ellis, Rod, (1999, p. 34). *Linguistic universals and second language acquisition: Mentalist theories of second language acquisition highlight the role of innate knowledge. This involves a language acquisition device that helps learners discover the grammatical rules of the target language. This device possesses an understanding of linguistic universals.* [5]

Analysis: Teaching methods may vary, but the basic cognitive processes remain the same. Effective methods should align with these natural processes.

- Fifth Principle: The process of vocabulary accumulation goes through several stages, starting with the recognition of foreign words, learning their meaning, and transforming the acquired words and grammatical knowledge into skills. People believe that learning transforms a living language into a skill. The acquisition of each foreign word is not a one-time event, but rather a process with several phases. We repeat the studied words multiple times during each phase to advance to the next, which is the acquisition of vocabulary and grammar. According to Nation (1990, as cited in Schmitt, 2000, p. 5) *suggests the subsequent list of a person must master various types of knowledge to gain a deeper understanding of word:*

- *the meaning(s) of the word*
- *the written form of the word*
- *the spoken form of the word*
- *the word's grammatical behavior*
- *the collocations of the word*
- *the register of the word*
- *the associations of the word*
- *the frequency of the word* [6]

Analysis: Acquiring new words and grammar is a step-by-step process. Repetition plays a crucial role in moving through different learning phases until words and grammatical rules become part of the learner's active vocabulary.

- Sixth Principle: The vocabulary of foreign words is divided into two categories: words used actively in dialogue and writing, forming the active vocabulary, and words used passively in listening and reading, understood in context and out of context, and those understood only in context. According to Nation, I.S.P. (2000, p. 38). *Receptive vocabulary uses entails identifying a word's form while listening or reading and retrieving its meaning. Effective vocabulary utilization necessitates the desire to articulate a meaning through speaking or writing, retrieving and producing the appropriate spoken or written expression written word form.* [7]

Analysis: Active and passive vocabulary serve different functions. Active vocabulary refers to words used in daily communication, whereas passive vocabulary refers to words understood in the context of reading and listening. This division helps focus efforts on different aspects of language acquisition.

- Seventh Principle: Effective methods for learning a foreign language include listening and reading, along with the ability to comprehend foreign speech or text. Active use of a foreign language, which transforms language knowledge into language skills, is a proven technique for acquisition. In this regard, it is advisable to focus on building a passive vocabulary in the early stages of learning a foreign language, and only after accumulating enough passive vocabulary can we move on to transforming it into an active vocabulary. According to Brown, H.D. (2007, p. 241). *Communicative Language Teaching: Listening and reading with comprehension are foundational techniques for language acquisition.*[8]

Analysis: Listening and reading with comprehension are foundational for building a passive vocabulary.

Once the learner accumulates a sufficient passive vocabulary, they can actively utilize the acquired words, thereby converting passive knowledge into active skills.

- Eighth Principle: The human mind controls the vital functions of the organism unconsciously, but the thought process engages a person's attention. A person's activated attention concentrates on a single specific thought. If a person observes another person speaking, they can focus their attention on what they hear or see, but not both. When speaking a foreign language, focus on what to say, not how. Placing the learner in an environment that engages their attention with unnecessary things diverts their focus. Even listening to pleasant and light music while learning can distract the learner's attention and worsen the learning outcome. According to Gilakjani, A.P. (2011). *Attention resources are crucial for learning, especially in second language acquisition. Consciousness is a product of an attention mechanism, which can be voluntarily controlled. Attention capacity is a limited resource and deals with psychological constraints. Attention is necessary for the conversion of input to intake and involves alertness, orientation, and detection.* [9]

Analysis: Focus is essential for effective learning. Conversations in a foreign language should concentrate on the content, not the process of speaking. Distractions, including background music, can reduce learning efficiency.

- Ninth Principle: Human capabilities to acquire foreign vocabulary are limited. We must assess and calculate the number of new words we will learn each day and the number of days we will repeat these words intensively and regularly, as a greater load (more new words) leads to a higher percentage of forgetting. Assuming the empirical rule of repeating new words studied daily for a month, we can calculate that at full load, after the first month, the total number of words for repetition is the daily number of new words multiplied by 30 days. As many teachers recommend, learning 3–4 new words a day will result in a daily repetition of 90–120 words. For each case, we can recalculate these numbers to determine two numbers: the number of new words per day and the number of days we will repeat these words. According to Hulstijn, J. H. (2001, p. 258-286). *Learning new words is complex because remembering word forms can be difficult, and the connection between a word's form and its meaning is purely arbitrary. Overcoming these challenges involves repeating words and understanding how these processes work.*[10]

Analysis: We can only effectively learn and remember a limited number of new words. Planned repetition is key to memorizing new words. We must determine the optimal number of words to learn and repeat daily for effective learning.

- Eleventh Principle: We can ensure the retention of active and passive language knowledge by actively and passively using them, respectively. Active use helps to maintain both active and passive knowledge. Passive use, such as listening or reading with comprehension, not only helps retain passive knowledge but also activates and transfers some of it to

the active vocabulary. The key to the success of this technique is the text—its complexity and the composition of words from the vocabulary used in the text. The vocabulary is built through accumulation. The vocabulary includes all studied words. We add new words to the vocabulary. We divide the studied words into two categories based on the planned repetitions. Each lesson's text includes new words studied in the previous 30 days for repetition. Texts repeat words studied more than 30 days ago once a week. According to Krahnke, K. (1987, p. 8-14). *Language teaching content, or syllabi, is a crucial aspect of teaching English as a second or foreign language. There are three types of syllabi: structural, situational, and notional/functional. Different approaches to syllabi design focus on language use and form, with methods involving both subject matter and linguistic matter.*[11]

Analysis: Maintaining language knowledge requires both active and passive use. Repeating new words in the context of texts is an effective method for retaining and activating knowledge.

- Twelfth Principle: Activating passive knowledge through dialogical exercises consisting of questions to which the learner must respond. This technique for acquiring a foreign language requires the learner to have previously learned and repeatedly refreshed the words used in the question sentences. We assume that the learner will know all the words and be able to respond when they hear or read the question sentence. Although the question may contain passive vocabulary words, it will help the respondent actively use them. According to Richards, J. (2008, p. 3-6). *The gap between understanding a language and being able to use it is a big issue. While learners understand more over time, their ability to use the language doesn't improve as much. Recognizing words doesn't mean being able to use them. Traditionally, teaching focused more on understanding than speaking. However, new theories say speaking skills need specific practice to develop. To close this gap, two things are needed: noticing language details and practicing focused speaking activities.* [12]

Analysis: Dialogical exercises are effective for activating passive knowledge. Questions should include previously learned words to help the learner use them actively in their responses.

- The Thirteenth Principle: Improving pronunciation through dialogue with a native speaker. Correct pronunciation is a sign of proficient mastery of a foreign language. Being in a language environment where native speakers practice the foreign language you've studied is the best way to deal with pronunciation. The longer the time spent in such an environment, the better the result. When communicating with a native speaker, it is necessary to follow the rule of proper etiquette to look the interlocutor in the eyes and mouth. Both parties usually use the same topic words in every conversation. The learner hears the correct pronunciation and then may need to repeat some words. Multiple hearings and pronunciations of the respective word led to improved pronunciation. Additionally, by observing the interlocutor's eyes and mouth, the observer subconsciously memorizes the movement of the speaker's

mouth muscles. This effect also contributes to excellent pronunciation. According to Yoshida, M.T. (2016, p.23). *Pronunciation involves learning new sounds by moving muscles in mouths and changing habits. It takes time and practice, requiring muscle memory and repeated practice to build speed and skill in pronunciation.*[13]

Analysis: Dialogue with native speakers is the most effective method for improving pronunciation. Visual observation of the interlocutor's mouth movements also helps better understand and reproduce correct pronunciation.

- Fourteenth principle: People can learn several foreign languages. So-called polyglots speak and write more than 5–10 foreign languages at a level sufficient for their free use. Polyglots have indivisible passive knowledge of all languages, so they can seamlessly switch between languages if their passive knowledge of the second language is not weaker than the first. In terms of active knowledge, things are different. When someone speaks to a polyglot in a foreign language that they know, the corresponding responses naturally come in the same language. However, switching to a different language during a conversation becomes more challenging for the polyglot. The language in which the conversation started is compelling, and the corresponding response comes naturally in the same language. In multilingualism, the active knowledge of individual foreign languages does not interfere with each other. Once a conversation in each foreign language has started, it continues naturally in the chosen language without any influence from the other languages. According to Erard, M. (2012, p. 189-204). *Hyperpolyglots are individuals with an innate talent for learning languages, often finding it easier than others. They are usually self-taught, but some learn with teachers and fellow students. According to a survey, hyperpolyglots who know six or more languages are rare, but not as rare as those who claim to know eleven or more. Most of them are men aged 25-40, with English as their mother tongue, and they tend to live in the same place where they grew up. Learning languages is easier for them, with 62% citing an innate talent, 69% being more motivated, and 88% stating they like languages. Despite their high linguistic abilities, hyperpolyglots' proficiency levels can vary significantly across different languages.*[14]

Analysis: Polyglots' abilities to learn and use multiple foreign languages highlight the differences between passive and active knowledge. While passive knowledge enables seamless language switching, active knowledge maintains a stronger connection to the original language of conversation.

- Fifteenth Principle: Mastery of multiple foreign languages entails the acquisition of several skills of a similar nature. Even after mastering multiple foreign languages, each skill remains independent and capable of autonomous application. In this context, we observe the following phenomenon in practice: when both participants converse in a foreign language, if one transitions to another language, they both know, the second participant may, usually unconsciously, switch

to the other language. In similar situations, it is challenging when both participants need to converse in different languages, and even more so if they need to switch languages mid-conversation. According to Erard, M. (2012, p. 93-102). *Polyglots have an extraordinary ability to learn and switch between multiple languages with ease, often demonstrating quick and accurate acquisition of new languages. They can master various writing systems and excel in constructing and spelling words, though their abilities may not extend to all aspects of language learning, such as sign language. The learning process for polyglots involves concentration, repetition, and practice, with motivation and perseverance being crucial factors. While some claim to know numerous languages, it's important to recognize the limits of language learning and be skeptical of exaggerated claims.*[15]

Analysis: The fact that mastering multiple languages leads to the development of several independent skills. The ability to transition unconsciously from one language to another when communicating with different interlocutors illustrates the flexibility of the human mind and its ability to adapt to diverse linguistic environments.

- Sixteenth Principle: There are two main ways to acquire a foreign language: implicit (natural, without a teacher) and explicit (intensive, with a teacher). Accepting the fact that children's first language teachers are their parents, we should recognize that these two methods apply equally to both native and foreign languages. There are no fundamental differences between the acquisition of native and foreign languages, as both methods can include elements of implicit and explicit learning. Implicit and explicit learning methods apply equally to both native and foreign languages. According to Ellis, N.C. (2011, p.35-45). *Explicit and implicit learning are two key approaches to language acquisition. Explicit learning involves conscious instruction and awareness of language rules, whereas implicit learning occurs naturally and subconsciously through exposure. Research supports that while implicit learning is essential for first language acquisition, explicit instruction significantly benefits second language acquisition (SLA) by enhancing the noticing of linguistic features and facilitating guided practice. Brain science shows that explicit learning is supported by the pre-frontal cortex, whereas implicit learning involves various perceptual and motor areas. The Weak Interface theory posits that explicit knowledge helps in the initial stages of learning, which is then refined through implicit processes during subsequent practice.*[16]

Analysis: This principle highlights the primary methods for language acquisition—implicit and explicit—that are applicable to both native and foreign languages. Although native language acquisition often occurs naturally with parents as the first language teachers, both methods of learning contain elements of implicit and explicit instruction. This underscores the flexibility of these approaches in language education, showing no fundamental difference in the acquisition of native and foreign languages.

- **Seventeenth Principle:** Learning a foreign language can be facilitated by using another foreign language as a leading language, provided the learner is proficient enough in the leading language to understand explanations about the target language. This creates synergy between the languages, benefiting both the leading and the target languages. Using a well-known foreign language as a leading language can enhance the learning process of another language. According to Butler, Y.G. (2013, p.109-130). *The study of bilingualism and multilingual acquisition looks at how people learn and use multiple languages, focusing on social and contextual factors. A key practice is learning a new language using another foreign language instead of the native one. This method shows how languages interact in the learner's mind. Multilingual acquisition varies based on factors like age, language differences, and the learning environment. Understanding this process involves both cognitive and social perspectives to grasp the complexity of using multiple languages.*[17]

Analysis: Using a well-known foreign language to learn another can leverage the learner's existing linguistic skills and understanding, thereby enhancing the learning process for both languages through interconnectedness and comparative learning.

- **Eighteenth Principle:** It is generally possible to learn two or more foreign languages simultaneously. When the two foreign languages belong to different language groups, the learner can more easily distinguish their vocabulary. When the levels of the two languages being studied are different, it is most reasonable to start with the language that is better mastered, followed by the one that is less proficient. Since the number of words learned per unit of time is limited, in cases where two foreign languages are studied simultaneously, the following effect can be sought: if usually 5 words are learned daily from one language, they can be reduced to 3-4 words, but the same number of words can be learned from the second language being studied in parallel. According to Baker, C. (2001, p.195-214). *Bilingual education, with a long history, has evolved to address the complexities of language acquisition. The theoretical aspect emphasizes learning two foreign languages simultaneously, highlighting cross-linguistic influences and the dynamic nature of language learning. This approach considers socio-contextual factors and promotes understanding of multiple languages in various domains. The practice of using one foreign language to learn another showcases the intricate process of acquiring multilingual competence.*[18]

Analysis: Simultaneous learning of two or more foreign languages is possible and can be effective, especially if the languages are from different language groups, which makes distinguishing the vocabulary easier. Allocating time and effort according to the proficiency level of the languages can optimize the learning process. Limiting the number of new words learned per day and distributing them between the two languages is a practical approach to managing workload and avoiding information overload.

This principle can be accepted as valid in the context of foreign language learning, as it is based on log-

ical arguments and practical experience. Although individual variations in the effectiveness of this approach may exist, it offers a rational method for simultaneous learning of two foreign languages.

- **Nineteenth Principle:** When learning a foreign language, one should not advance with new material if the current material is not well understood. This phenomenon is characteristic of intensive language learning. In such situations, it is advisable, when necessary, to slow down the pace of new material, or even temporarily stop introducing new material, and instead review and practice previously learned material. The same applies to vocabulary. When the accumulated passive vocabulary, which is understood only in context, increases, it is recommended to engage in listening and reading with comprehension of texts that are at an appropriate level of complexity and difficulty for the learner. According to Wolf, M., Muijselaar, M., Boonstra, A., Bree, E. (2018). *The comprehension process involves both reading and listening, with a focus on understanding information from different formats. Listening comprehension, often overlooked in education, plays a critical role alongside reading comprehension in children's learning and lifelong education. Research highlights that while both types of comprehension are related, they also possess modality-specific skills like attention and memory. Understanding these relationships is crucial for improving educational practices and supporting the development of comprehensive skills across modalities. Further research is needed to explore these modality-specific processes and their implications for educational interventions.*[19]

Analysis: Halting progress with new material and focusing on review and practice of already learned content is an important approach in foreign language acquisition. This allows the learner to consolidate their knowledge and avoid overload with new information. Especially in intensive learning, it is necessary to provide enough time for thorough understanding and assimilation of material, leading to more effective learning and better results.

- **Twentieth Principle:** Vocabulary is best learned in context, but this can be developed further by adding the study of related words within the text. For example, if the word "engine" is to be learned, it is advisable to add 2-3 related words, such as different types of engines: electric engine, gasoline engine, and diesel engine. This way, the learner will understand the different types of engines and their specifics in a broader context. When learning the different types of engines separately, it facilitates the acquisition and organization of vocabulary in the learner's memory. According to Garza, B. & Harris, R. (2016). *Language learning involves acquiring vocabulary through contextual strategies, crucial for comprehension and skill development. Research explores how the effectiveness of these strategies diminishes as the number of unfamiliar words per sentence increases. The Involvement Load Hypothesis highlights that task complexity affects learning outcomes, emphasizing the need for optimal levels of comprehensible input to facilitate effective vocabulary ac-*

quisition. Understanding these dynamics informs educational practices aimed at maximizing language learning through strategic use of linguistic context.[20]

Analysis: Learning vocabulary in the context of a text, especially by adding related words, is an effective method for memorizing and understanding new words. This helps build a connected and deep knowledge base, which facilitates recall and use of the words in real situations. Learning words in their natural relationships and contexts creates stronger associations in memory, leading to more sustainable and effective language acquisition.

4. Research

This study addresses the above 15 principles of foreign language learning. The research consists of surveys in relation to the principles. The polls are open and there is no limit to the number of participants. The Facebook platform is used, where a special group is created for research in connection with learning foreign languages: [21]

- Question: What distractions most affect your ability to focus while learning a foreign language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Background music: 25%
- Noisy environment: 25%
- Multitasking: 50%
- Visual distractions:
- None, I can focus easily:

- Question: What stage do you find most challenging in vocabulary acquisition?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Recognizing foreign words: 2%
- Understanding the meaning of words: 2%
- Transforming words into active skills: 23%
- Retaining vocabulary over time: 73%

- Do you agree that the mental processes for learning a foreign language are the same as those for learning a native language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Strongly agree: 60%
- Agree: 8%
- Neutral: 0%
- Disagree: 16%
- Strongly disagree: 16%

- What is the most effective way for children to learn their native language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Through interaction with parents: 54%
- By paying and engaging in activities: 41%
- Though structured lessons and repetition: 1%
- By watching educational programs: 4%

- How important is it to understand how people acquire their native language when learning a foreign language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Very important: 18%
- Important: 64%
- Somewhat important: 17%
- Not important: 1%

- How do you evaluate your progress in learning a foreign language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- By tracking the number of new words learned: 1%

- By evaluating my ability to use the language in real-life situations: 78%

- By taking regular tests: 15%

- By seeking feedback from native speakers: 5%

- By reviewing past mistakes and improvements: 1%

- What should be the ratio between implicit (unconscious) and explicit (deliberate) foreign language learning?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- 0% implicit (unconscious) / 100% explicit (deliberate): 2%

- 20% implicit (unconscious) / 80% explicit (deliberate): 24%

- 40% implicit (unconscious) / 60% explicit (deliberate): 45%

- 50% implicit (unconscious) / 100% explicit (deliberate): 21%

- 60% implicit (unconscious) / 40% explicit (deliberate): 2%

- 80% implicit (unconscious) / 20% explicit (deliberate): 5%

- 100% implicit (unconscious) / 0% explicit (deliberate): 1%

- What do you think is the most challenging part of learning a new language?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Grammar and syntax rules: 21%

- Pronunciation and accent: 5%

- Vocabulary retention: 10%

- Listening comprehension: 15%

- Speaking fluently and confidently: 11%

- Writing correctly: 3%

- Cultural nuances and idiomatic expressions: 26%

- It always depends on language: 3%

- all above are equally challenging: 3%

- What aspects of language learning do you find most enjoyable?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Speaking and having conversations: 22%

- Understanding and interpreting media: 14%

- Learning about the culture related to the language: 22%

- Reading and understanding written texts: 30%

- Achieving milestones and seeing progress: 12%

- How do you incorporate foreign language practice into your daily routine?

Selected replies with temporary results:

- Setting aside specific study times each day: 12%

- Integrating language learning into daily activities: 23%

- Using language learning apps during commutes or breaks: 12%

- Practicing with friends or family members: 22%

- Consuming media in the foreign language (e.g. music, movies, books): 31%

5. Conclusion:

The principles for learning a foreign language outlined in this study provide a comprehensive and structured framework for effective language acquisition.

The research, supported by survey data, emphasizes the importance of understanding the natural processes of language learning, applying practical use, and maintaining a balanced approach to vocabulary acquisition and retention. Key conclusions include:

1. Self-Evaluation and Strategy Selection: Successful language learners must regularly evaluate their progress and select appropriate strategies for effective acquisition. This involves choosing methods that align with individual learning styles and preferences.

2. Natural Language Acquisition Processes: Understanding how people naturally acquire their native language is crucial for foreign language learning. Methods that mimic these natural processes, focusing on comprehension and contextual learning, tend to be more effective than rote memorization.

3. Role of Context and Interaction: Practical use of language in natural settings, such as interactions with native speakers or immersive environments, is essential. This mirrors how children learn their native language through communication and contextual understanding.

4. Cognitive Consistency: Regardless of the teaching methods employed, the cognitive processes involved in language learning remain consistent. Effective methods should align with these natural cognitive functions to enhance learning outcomes.

5. Phased Vocabulary Acquisition and Retention: Building vocabulary is a multi-stage process that requires repeated exposure and practical use. This includes distinguishing between active and passive vocabulary and using targeted methods to develop both.

6. Listening and Reading for Comprehension: These foundational techniques support the transition from passive to active language use. Comprehension-focused activities help reinforce vocabulary and grammatical structures.

7. Maintaining Focus: Minimizing distractions in the learning environment is critical for maintaining concentration and effectiveness. Strategies to enhance focus include creating a quiet study space and avoiding multitasking.

8. Controlled Learning Load: To prevent cognitive overload and forgetting, learners should manage the amount of new vocabulary introduced daily. Regular, planned repetition is essential for long-term retention.

9. Active and Passive Use: Sustaining language knowledge requires a combination of active practice (speaking and writing) and passive use (listening and reading). Text complexity and vocabulary composition play key roles in retention.

10. Dialogical Exercises: Engaging in dialogues and responding to questions helps activate passive knowledge, making it part of the learner's active vocabulary through practical use.

11. Pronunciation Improvement: Conversing with native speakers and observing their mouth movements significantly enhance pronunciation skills, leading to more accurate and natural speech.

12. Insights from Polyglots: Polyglots demonstrate the capacity to learn and use multiple languages effectively. Their ability to switch seamlessly between languages underscores the importance of both passive

and active knowledge. While passive knowledge allows for smooth transitions, active knowledge maintains a strong connection to the language of conversation.

The survey results reinforce these principles, highlighting common challenges and preferences among language learners. For instance, retaining vocabulary over time is identified as a significant challenge, while practical use and interaction are seen as crucial for effective learning. These findings underscore the need for a balanced, interactive, and contextual approach to language acquisition.

By adhering to these principles and leveraging insights from both theoretical and practical research, learners can optimize their language learning process. This holistic approach ensures comprehensive and long-lasting language skills, enabling learners to achieve proficiency and confidence in using foreign languages.

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